

Open Source and Commercial Large Language Models comparison:

The performance capability and limitation of Open Source Large Language Models for geoparsing tasks

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To cite this paper: Chang, J.; Wu, C; Noennig, J. (2025) The performance capability and limitation of open source large language models for geoparsing tasks. FOSSGIS 2025 Tagungsband. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14616472>

Summary:

Geoparsing is a process that combines *Name Entity Recognition* (NER) and *Geocoding* to process free text and identify geolocalized terms in them, which are then converted into spatial coordinates using Geocoder API. On such premise, here presented research project is part of a cooperation with the Real Estate Management Corporation of the city of Hamburg (LIG) and pursues the overarching goal of developing a geoparsing workflow for processing the open source database of the Hamburg Parliament. Specifically, the aim is to link and visualize neighbourhood land parcels that are part of public discussion - for which a large number of PDF files are to be processed and visualized on a WebGIS system. For this aim, we are now investigating the functional capabilities and limitations of Large Language Models (LLM). In order to accurately estimate how many place terms are recognized, we have developed a validation workflow (including a process to spatially join multiple geocoded point coordinates) that automatically compares and calculates the percentage of place terms recognized by each model. With the rapid development of LLM, it has become easy to extract corresponding location lists - but the quality of results has remained an open question. This research paper therefore focuses on the performance of open-source LLMs, of which we have tested *Meta Llama3.1-70b-instruct* and *Mistral-large-2* in order to compare them with *Claude-sonnet-3.5-new* and *OpenAI o1-preview*. For the geocoding process the geocoders *Nominatim* and *Mapbox Geocoder API* are used. For addresses with house numbers, we use the official address sources published by the State Corporation For Geoinformation and Surveying (LGV). The results show that a hybrid approach of combined LLM can extract up to 74,98% of unique locations from the text, including the full address with house numbers while Claude, on the other hand, only achieves 53%. We also found that open source LLMs are limited in extracting the names of institutions (e.g. high schools) without giving concrete address information from the texts. Such edge cases will be further illustrated in the discussion session.

Keywords:

Geoparsing, Name Entity Recognition, Geocoding, Llama, Mistral, Nominatim

1. Introduction and previous research

Geoparsing is a process that combines Name Entity Recognition (NER) and Geocoding to process free-text and identify geolocation terminology, and further uses geocoder API to convert from location texts into coordinates. Previous research by Ventrice & Di Caro (2023) [6] explored text extraction from Wikipedia data, focusing on the public knowledge graph's spatial accuracy, emphasizing advancements in NER to enhance location-based information accuracy. There are many ways to detect location / addresses / place names from long texts. When applying to German texts, the most popular approaches are the *flair-german-large* and *BERT* model (Tao et.al, 2022) [5]. Here represent research cooperation project, we are jointly working on scientific context with Hamburg's Real Estate Management Corporation (Landesbetrieb Immobilienmanagement und Grundvermögen, LIG) focusing on developing a **geoparsing workflow** for processing data from Hamburg's open source Parliament Database (Dally et.al, 2024) [3]. To discover public discussions related to real-estate land properties, we aimed at processing large amounts of PDF files and visualizing them on a webGIS platform developed by HCU chair of Digital City Science in cooperation with LIG – the AGORA tool. In an earlier project phase, the *flair/ner-german-large* [7] model was used to extract locations from texts (Mellow & Chang, 2023) [4]. In this research, the focus of the investigation was on an exemplary local newspaper, "Elbewochenblatt"; the geoparsed results (including topic modeling) were visualized as point clusters in the AGORA toolbox [8].

2. Methodologies

2.1 Geoparsing Workflow

In order to support the routine tasks of the LIG workers, a powerful geoparsing workflow is required, with the focus on 1) location recognition including house numbers, and 2) accurate geocoding of the spatial map coordinates. With the rapid growth of LLMs, we can easily prompt the systems in order to extract location lists.

Below is a prompt example :

Extract all place names or addresses in Hamburg from the input text and enter them in the following format: 'Street name, house number, district'. Please note:

- a. Each address should be in separate lines.
- b. If there are several house numbers on the same street, create separate lines with the complete address for each house number.
- c. Terms that represent both the location and the name of an organisation should be included in the result list.

- d. Only extract locations and addresses in Hamburg.
- e. Skip the terms of 'Hamburg' or 'Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg'.
- f. The output text should not contain any irrelevant words or text phrases.
- g. Only use the information available in the input text.

Conversely, we found that the flair model is not able to identify complete addresses including house numbers. Therefore, we investigated whether modern LLM can carry out the same task and checked - in order to better evaluate the results - how many location terms are eventually detected. Figure 1 shows the implementation diagram of our geoparsing workflow:

Figure 1 Geoparsing workflow

For the geocoding tasks, we have integrated three approaches. For those addresses in Hamburg having house numbers, we adapt the official published address from the city of Hamburg (Landesbetrieb Geoinformation und Vermessung, LGV). For the remaining addresses, Mapbox geocoder API and the open source geocoder Nominatim were used.

2.2 NER Validation

To achieve significant savings in terms of human labour costs and to address the challenge of the fast iterated versions of LLMs, we have developed a validation workflow that includes a process for geocoding and spatial joining of the same location term from different model results. This workflow enables the automatic comparison and calculation of the percentage of location terms that have been detected from each LLM model. We have deployed Ollama [9] on High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters [10] to run the open source LLM Mistral-large-2 and LLama 3.1-70b-Instruct.

We have further selected 33 smaller parliamentary requests (Schriftliche Kleine Anfragen, SKA) which include 1,612 locations as samples. Many of them include long

appendices that contain most locations and addresses. We have further invited German native speakers to label these texts (as human labels), and deployed different LLM to process the text, document for each location which model successfully detected it, and further join these locations from different models into the same row. We have aligned our validation table as shown in table 1.

Table 1 Validation table

human_label	claude	llama	mistral	o1_preview	Check
Alsterdorfer Straße 39			Alsterdorfer Straße 39	Alsterdorfer Straße 39	TP
Alter Postweg 30	Alter Postweg 30			Alter Postweg 30	TP
Anna Susanna-Stieg 3					FN
Auf dem Sülzbrack 2	Auf dem Sülzbrack 2	Auf dem Sülzbrack 2			TP
Außenmühlenweg 23a	Außenmühlenweg 23a		Außenmühlenweg 23a	Außenmühlenweg 23a	TP
Baakenallee 33					FN
Bad Billstedt Archenholzstraße 50a			Archenholzstraße 50a		TP
Dratelnstraße 21	Dratelnstraße 21	Dratelnstraße 21		Dratelnstraße 21	TP
Georg-Wilhelm-Straße 112	Georg-Wilhelm-Straße 112	Georg-Wilhelm-Straße 112	Georg-Wilhelm-Straße 112	Georg-Wilhelm-Straße 112	TP
		Sozialtherapeutische Anstalt			FP

Column “Check” was first given by automatic script and further checked by a second human validator. TP stands for “True-Positive” and means that both human and LLM have determined this term as location. FN stands for “False-Negative”, meaning that the LLM did not detect this actually existing location; and FP stands for “False-Positive”, meaning that the LLM extracted a location while humans determined this being no location. We do not have TN “True-Negative” information, since we did not preserve texts that are not locations from prompt results.

To align this validation table, it would take a lot of copy and paste time from several location lists of different LLM models. Therefore, we developed a spatial joining approach, that is able to 1) automatically geocode location or address into coordinates, and 2) *spatially outer join* every two of them, with a predefined joining buffer of 5 meters radius. In this approach, when human labels e.g. “Alster-Schwimmhalle Ifflandstraße 21” but LLM only extracts “Ifflandstraße 21”, this location will be labeled as TP. There are also scenarios where: 1) a location can not be geocoded or geocoded outside of Hamburg, and 2) no specific location is given, e.g. “Elbepark” or “Senatsparkplatz” - such edge cases we have eliminated from our validation table.

To better follow European GDPR regulation, before processing commercial LLM we removed all person names from the text. Additionally, the GPU cluster center

processing open source LLM is within the EU and is certified with data protection regulation.

3. Results

For ChatGPT o1-preview results, we were unable to process all 33 SKAs due to HCU currently developing new AI regulations and guidelines, that prevented a subscription to OpenAI. Hence, we were only able to process 1 SKA. With Claude from Anthropic AI, however, we were able to process all 33 sample datasets. Mistral and Llama we processed on Karolina HPC cluster with Ollama. For each model, we found that smaller models (such as Mistral-8b or Llama 3.1-8b) are much more likely to produce hallucinations in the prompt result. They also have disadvantages as they easily ignore middle contexts and only extract location from the beginning and the ending of a paragraph. Therefore, we only choose large models to process SKAs.

To tackle hallucination, it is necessary to program a post-processing script to remove location that do not exist in SKAs, so that these false addresses will not be geocoded.

Table 2 illustrates how many percent of the location was extracted for 33 sample SKAs.

Table 3 represent both flair-german-large and o1-preview model, only 1 SKA were evaluated.

Table 2 Model results I (33 SKAs, 1612 rows)

Models / Fundamental Metrics tests	Llama3.1-70b-instruct	Mistral Large-2	Claude 3.5-Sonnet	Hybrid (without deepseek)	Deepseek R1:70b
Sensitivity TP / (TP + FN)	34,16 %	55,10 %	48,90 %	68,41 %	48.15%
Precision TP / (TP + FP)	95,36 %	91,81 %	93,90%	87,52%	87.38%
F1 Score	0.5030	0.6880	0.6431	0.768	0.621

Table 3 Model results II (1 SKA, 341 rows)

Models / Tests	Claude 3.5-Sonnet	Llama3.1-70b-instruct	Mistral Large-2	Flair-german-large	ChatGPT o1-preview	Deepseek R1:70b
<u>TP</u>	213	46	42	58	175	69
<u>FP</u>	11	18	4	615	29	63
<u>FN</u>	128	295	299	283	166	194

Models / Tests	Claude 3.5-Sonnet	Llama3.1-70b-instruct	Mistral Large-2	Flair-german-large	ChatGPT o1-preview	Deepseek R1:70b
Sensitivity TP / (TP + FN)	62,5 %	13,49 %	12,31 %	17,01 %	51,32 %	26,24%
Precision TP / (TP + FP)	95,1 %	71,9 %	91,3 %	8,61 %	85,8 %	52,3%
F1 Score	0.7539	0.2272	0.2171	0.1144	0.6422	0.349

Notes:

$F1 \text{ Score} = 2 * (\text{Precision} * \text{Sensitivity}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Sensitivity})$

Interpretation of F1: Moderate: 0.4-0.6; Good: 0.6-0.8; Excellent: 0.8-1 ; All formula reference Carterette, B. (2009) [2]

Table 3 represents Claude as the best model, according to F1 score. Despite Flair-german-large extract the largest number of TP compared with open source LLMs, its large number of FP (false location that can be geocoded) lead to a very low F1 score.

When combining methods and calculating the sensitivity ratio, a coverage of 74,98% correct location assignments is reached. Even though fake locations (FP) are a concern, however, most false locations are either being eliminated by prompt response post processing script and thus not geocoded, or being geocoded outside of Hamburg so not included in the WebGIS system.

4. Discussion

Definition of "Edge Cases":

While implementing NER validation, we found there are some special location terms, e.g. Tiefgarage (underground parking) or elementary school Eimsbüttel; which however refer to **non-specific** or **multiple** locations. Such cases may only be geocoded into a **single location** or **not in Hamburg** at all. Some institution names are hard to detect by open source LLM e.g. terms like "**Molotow**", the Hamburg-Mitte District Office, the Ministry of Urban Development and Housing, the Ministry of Culture and Media, the Ministry of Schools and Vocational Training, or the Jewish Community in Hamburg.. Other difficult cases are planning sites for future city development, e.g. a replacement building for the Finkenwerder fire brigade and rescue station (here only Finkenwerder was geoparsed).

There are also scenarios that a specific area is mentioned, e.g. "**a conjunction of road entries near town hall and extension to 100 meters in the direction of Adolphs**

Bridge”. Our workflow is currently not able to tackle these challenges, however, it is a good use case to further work with spatial AI in the near future.

In terms of open source LLM, we found Mistral is a more “talkative” model than Llama. Sometimes it does not follow our prompt instruction and produces additional information in response. However, through our post processing script, some institution names were captured and geoparsed, which may lead to higher TP for some SKAs.

As a conventional model, the *flair-german-large* brings more “**stable**” results than commercial or open source LLMs. This is to say, no matter how many times the *flair* model was run, it always reproduces the same results, which is not achieved by LLMs - they may generate different results for each run. For open source models this “instability” is more likely to happen than for commercial LLMs.

Our geoparsing and validation approach can be easily adapted to **other languages** and for **a variety of data types**, like journal articles, wikipedia or social media posts. In such scenario, **language-specific** LLM should be considered (for example: to process Chinese traditional datasets one should consider “MediaTek LLMs [11]). It is also important to search for a region specific geocoder (ideally provided by the local government) to improve the sensitivity ratio.

Following the NER validation, the project will focus on fine-tuning an open source language model in the upcoming months. We will test open source models with a parameter size of 7b or 70b- depending on the availability of GPU resources and with the help of model / data parallelism. The medium-term goal is to develop a chatbot that is able to answer questions on specific urban development topics such as “Densification”, “Pre-Emption Rights” and “Main Avenue Planning”.

5. Funding Statement

The research was supported by funding from Landesbetrieb Immobilienmanagement und Grundvermögen Hamburg (LIG).

6. Acknowledgements

This study was part of one work package within the third phase of HCU’s collaborative research project with LIG Hamburg, which aims to discover modern AI using Geoparsing in an urban governance perspective. We also thank Ms. Cheng-Chia Wu, our DAAD summer intern who developed a prototype of the spatial join validation workflow.

7. Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare. The *Landesbetrieb Immobilienmanagement und Grundvermögen Hamburg (LIG)* had no influence on the content of this article.

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